

Convergence and constraint in the cranial evolution of mosasaurid reptiles and early cetaceans

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Supplementary information

Institutional abbreviations

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Morphological ratios

1. Tooth shape (tooth crown height : crown base width)

Characterises resistance to bite forces in the tooth crown (Massare 1987; Fischer et al. 2016).

The tooth chosen was from the anterior part of the rostrum or mandible, and was neither procumbent (e.g. *Prognathodon* (Lingham-Soliar and Nolf 1989)) nor a tusk (e.g.

Ankylorhiza (Boessenecker et al. 2020)).

2. Absolute tooth crown size (tooth crown height raw measurement)

This has been shown to strongly correlate with prey size in modern cetaceans (Ridgeway and Harrison 1999).

3. Relative orbit diameter (orbit diameter : skull length)

The internal diameter of the sclerotic ring has been used as a proxy for visual acuity in ichthyosaurs (Motani et al. 1999; Fischer et al. 2016). As the sclerotic ring is not present in cetaceans we used the maximum diameter of the orbit. For more derived cetaceans this was estimated from the distance between the preorbital and postorbital processes of the frontal.

In order to standardise measurements between mosasaurids and cetaceans, our skull length measurement was taken from the snout tip to the posterior-most point of the skull at the temporal arcade, and thus does not equate to condylobasal length previously used for cetaceans (Pyenson and Sponberg 2011).

4. Relative snout length (snout length : skull length)

Modified from (Fischer et al. 2020) to be based on skull length rather than mandible length. Related to the (i) resistance of the skull to lateral shaking of prey (ii) the effects of drag during swimming and (iii) the volume of water required to be displaced during the opening and closing of the snout.

5. Relative snout depth (snout depth at the midpoint : snout length)

Related to the resistance of the skull to lateral shaking of prey, as well as reinforcement for bite forces. Modified from (Fischer et al. 2016). Snout depth was taken perpendicular to the palate (rather than from the lateral edge to the midpoint, which would have resulted in erroneously large values for taxa with flat snouts such as *Aetiocetus*). For some taxa from both clades the midpoint of the snout falls within the external nares – in these cases the measurement was taken as preserved, however it should be noted that this may result in a slight overestimation of the ratio value.

6. Relative snout width (snout width just before orbit : snout length)

Related to the volume of water needed to be expelled for jaw closure (Fischer et al. 2020). In cetaceans the snout width measurement was taken at the antorbital notch.

7. Anterior mechanical advantage

The mandible is modelled as a lever, with the articulation point with the skull acting as a fulcrum and input force applied from the adductor muscles (Anderson 2009; Anderson et al.

2011; Stubbs and Benton 2016; MacLaren et al. 2017). Mechanical advantage is calculated as the ratio of inlever to outlever moment arms.

The anterior mechanical advantage (AMA) is the lowest potential mechanical advantage (Stubbs and Benton 2016). The inlever is the distance between the adductor muscle insertion (coronoid process) and the fulcrum, and the outlever is the distance from the fulcrum to the anterior-most point on the dentary tooth row. A low value for AMA equates to a weak rapid bite, whereas a high value equates to one which is slower and more forceful (Stubbs and Benton 2016).

8. Opening mechanical advantage

This is a proxy for the velocity during jaw opening (MacLaren et al. 2017). The inlever is the distance from the fulcrum to the retroarticular process (in mosasaurs) or the angular process (in cetaceans), and the outlever is the distance from the tip of the dentary tooth row to the fulcrum.

9. Temporal musculature (temporal fenestra length : skull length)

Characteristics of the temporal region have previously been used to draw conclusions on bite force in both fossil cetaceans (Lambert et al. 2014; Benites-Palomino et al. 2020) and mosasaurs (Lingham-Soliar 1995). The above calculation was used by Russell (1975).

10. Relative symphysis length (symphysis length : mandible length)

Characterises snout shape as well as resistance to forces during biting (Fischer et al. 2020). As most mosasaurids and some early cetaceans do not have a sutured symphysis (Fitzgerald 2012; Stubbs and Benton 2016), we measured the area of ligamentous contact between mandibles.

Table S2. Stomach contents and previous ecological interpretations.

Taxon	Stomach contents	Other	Pauly diet class	Sources
<i>Cynthiacetus peruvianus</i>	Large scombrid fish, may have caused death	NA	Apex	(Martínez-Cáceres et al. 2017)
<i>Dorudon atrox</i>	Fish	NA	Fish	(Uhen 2004; Fahlke et al. 2013)
<i>Basilosaurus isis</i>	Juvenile <i>Dorudon</i> , large fish, fish and sharks up to 50cm	NA	Apex	(Swift and Barnes 1996; Fahlke et al. 2013; Voss et al. 2019)
<i>Kekenodon</i> sp.	NA	Isotopes suggest lower trophic level	NA	(Clementz et al. 2014)
<i>Mystacodon selenensis</i>	NA	Tooth wear suggests possible feeder of benthic fish	Fish	(Lambert et al. 2017; de Muizon et al. 2019)
<i>Coronodon havensteini</i>	NA	Tooth filter feeding and/or raptorial	NA	(Geisler et al. 2017; Hocking et al. 2017)

<i>Janjucetus hunderi</i>	NA	Raptorial feeding	NA	(Fitzgerald 2006)
<i>Aetiocetus weltonii</i>	NA	Small prey, possibly by bulk feeding/baleen	NA	(Deméré and Berta 2008; Marx et al. 2016; Ekdale and Deméré 2021)
<i>Aetiocetus cotylalveus</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Simocetus rayi</i>	NA	Lack of premaxillary teeth, delicate cheek teeth, deflected rostral tip	Benthic, soft bodied	(Fordyce 2002)
<i>Agorophius</i> sp.	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Cotylocara macei</i>	NA	Echolocation	NA	(Geisler et al. 2014)
<i>Waipatia maerewhenua</i>	NA	Tusks	NA	(Fordyce 1994)
<i>Ankylorhiza tiedemani</i>	NA	Tusks	NA	(Boessenecker et al. 2020)
<i>Xenorophus</i> sp.	NA	No tusks	NA	Pers. obs.
<i>Eosqualodon</i> sp.	NA	Tusks	NA	Pers. obs.
OU 22397	NA	Tusks	NA	Pers. obs.
<i>Halisaurus arambourgi</i>	NA	'Plioplatecarpus-like teeth'	NA	(Bardet et al. 2005, 2015; Lindgren and Siverson 2005)

<i>Russellosaurus coheni</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Tethysaurus nopcsai</i>	NA	No carinae	NA	(Bardet et al. 2003)
<i>Ectenosaurus clidastoides</i>	NA	Short predental rostrum	NA	(Polcyn and Everhart 2008)
<i>Selmasaurus johnsoni</i>	NA	Short predental rostrum	NA	(Polcyn and Everhart 2008)
<i>Platecarpus tympaniticus</i>	Fish of a range of sizes (up to 1.2m)	NA	Apex/fish	(Williston 1899; Russell 1967; Lindgren et al. 2010)
<i>Plesioplatecarpus</i> sp.	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Plioplatecarpus</i> sp.	Belemnites	Edentulous region on dentary, large brain	Squid	(Dollo 1913; Lingham-Soliar 1994)
<i>Tylosaurus proriger</i>	Plesiosaur, small mosasaurs, bird, teleost fish, shark, cephalopod	NA	Apex	(Williston 1898; Martin and Bjork 1987; Stewart and Carpenter 1990; Everhart 2004)
<i>Tylosaurus bernardi</i>	Turtle bones in body cavity	NA	Apex	(Dollo 1887)
<i>Tylosaurus nepaeolicus</i>	Small mosasaurs	NA	Apex	(Everhart 2008)

<i>Gavialimimus almaghribensis</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Clidastes</i> sp.	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Mosasaurus</i> sp IRSNB R12	NA	Tooth facets	NA	(Lingham-Soliar 1995)
<i>Mosasaurus missouriensis</i>	Aulopiform fish (>1m)	NA	Apex	(Konishi et al. 2014)
<i>Mosasaurus lemonnieri</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Globidens dakotensis</i>	Bivalves	Bulbous teeth without carinae	Benthic, hard bodied	(Martin and Fox 2007)
<i>Prognathodon solvayi</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Prognathodon overtoni</i>	Sea turtle, fish up to 1.6m, cephalopod, possibly ammonites	NA	Apex	(Kauffman and Kesling 1960; Konishi et al. 2011)
<i>Prognathodon currii</i>	NA	NA	NA	
<i>Plotosaurus bennisoni</i>	Fish	NA	Fish	(Camp 1942)

Notes on dietary classification

As stomach contents are only a snapshot of an organism's diet and are biased by the preservation potential of the prey (Pollard 1968), we considered other ecological features noted by previous studies. Dietary classes were modified from Pauly *et al* (1998) and Kelley & Motani (2015).

- Apex: capable of eating food which cannot be swallowed whole, and must be torn into chunks. These animals likely ate a generalist diet which included large marine vertebrates and large fish.
- Fish/squid: diet of small fish and squid which can be swallowed whole or with little oral processing.
- Benthic: diet of benthic invertebrates, which can be either soft bodied or hard bodied, and likely required some level of oral processing to remove sediment and/or the shell.

The evolutionary origins of baleen filter feeding in mysticetes are highly debated. Several of the taxa included in this analysis fall within this debate. *Coronodon* was originally proposed to be a tooth filter feeder (Geisler et al. 2017) however another study looking into the sharpness of teeth suggests raptorial feeder (Hocking et al. 2017). Likewise, there is evidence that baleen was present alongside teeth in *Aetiocetus* (Deméré et al. 2008; Ekdale and Deméré 2021). The ratios for this study are based on raptorial feeding, and we chose to include *Coronodon* and *Aetiocetus* as both have functional, fully erupted teeth (Deméré and Berta 2008; Geisler et al. 2017). We do not assess the potential of either taxa to use bulk filter feeding in this study, and given the debate over *Coronodon*'s diet chose to leave it as NA.

Table S3. Locomotion style.

Taxon	Locomotion style	Source
<i>Cynthiacetus peruvianus</i>	Sub-carangiform	(Martínez-Cáceres et al. 2017)
<i>Dorudon atrox</i>	Sub-carangiform	(Uhen 2004)
<i>Basilosaurus isis</i>	Anguilliform	(Buchholtz 2001)
<i>Kekenodon</i> sp.	NA	
<i>Mystacodon selenensis</i>	NA	
<i>Coronodon havensteini</i>	NA	
<i>Janjucetus hunderi</i>	NA	
<i>Aetiocetus weltonii</i>	NA	
<i>Aetiocetus cotylalveus</i>	Anguilliform	(Buchholtz 2001)
<i>Simocetus rayi</i>	NA	
<i>Agorophius</i> sp.	NA	
<i>Cotylocara macei</i>	NA	
<i>Waipatia maerewhenua</i>	NA	
<i>Ankylorhiza tiedemani</i>	Carangiform	(Boessenecker et al. 2020)
<i>Xenorophus</i> sp.	NA	
<i>Eosqualodon</i> sp.	NA	
OU 22397	NA	
<i>Halisaurus arambourgi</i>	NA	
<i>Russellosaurus coheni</i>	Anguilliform	(Polcyn and Bell 2005)
<i>Tethysaurus nopcsai</i>	Anguilliform	(Bardet et al. 2003)
<i>Ectenosaurus clidastoides</i>	Sub-carangiform	(Lindgren et al. 2011a)
<i>Selmasaurus johnsoni</i>	NA	

<i>Platecarpus tympaniticus</i>	Carangiform	(Lindgren et al. 2010)
<i>Plesioplatecarpus planifrons</i>	NA	
<i>Plioplatecarpus</i> sp.	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Tylosaurus proriger</i>	Carangiform	(Carpenter 2017)
<i>Tylosaurus bernardi</i>	NA	
<i>Tylosaurus nepaeolicus</i>	NA	
<i>Gavialimimus almaghribensis</i>	NA	
<i>Clidastes</i> sp.	Sub-carangiform	(Lindgren et al. 2011b)
<i>Mosasaurus</i> aff. <i>hoffmanni</i>	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Mosasaurus missouriensis</i>	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Mosasaurus lemonnierii</i>	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Globidens dakotensis</i>	NA	
<i>Prognathodon solvayi</i>	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Prognathodon overtoni</i>	Carangiform	(Lindgren et al. 2013)
<i>Prognathodon currii</i>	NA (see discussion below)	
<i>Plotosaurus bennisoni</i>	Near-thunniform	(Lindgren et al. 2007)

Notes on locomotion

Locomotory classes were modified from Lindgren *et al* (Lindgren et al. 2011b) and Buchholtz (Buchholtz 2001), with taxa classified according to previous work (electronic supplementary material, Table S3).

- Anguilliform: undulatory locomotion using the entire vertebral column, elongate eel-like body shape

- Sub-carangiform: some adaptations towards restricting undulations at the anterior-most part of the vertebral column and body
- Carangiform: further stiffening and shortening of body, motion restricted to the posterior-most part of the body and tail
- Thunniform: locomotion entirely tail-driven

Despite the evidence that *Prognathodon overtoni* was carangiform, we chose to leave *P. solvayi* and *P. curri* as NA due to variation within the genus. Likewise, Lindgren *et al* (2011b) classified several specimens of *Mosasaurus* as sub-carangiform, however we chose not to expand this to the three species included in this study. It has been proposed that *Plioplatecarpus* used a style of forelimb driven locomotion unique among mosasaurs (Lingham-Soliar 1992), however this has been disputed (Holmes et al. 1999). As forelimb shape is not considered in this study, we left its locomotion style as NA.

Table S4. Results of Stayton convergence tests with with the node determined by the minimum branch length (i.e., divergence in the Aptian), reported to four decimal places. * indicates significance at $p < 0.05$, ** at $p < 0.01$, and *** at $p < 0.001$. M = Mosasauridae; C = Cetacea; Mos = Mosasaurina; Rus = Russellosaurina; Odo = Odontoceti; Mys = Mysticeti.

Taxon pair	PCo axes	C1	p-value
<i>Janjucetus hunderi</i> (C) –	PCo1-2	0.0000	0.9990
	All	0.0000	0.9990
<i>Prognathodon solvayi</i> (M)			
<i>Basilosaurus isis</i> (C) –	PCo1-2	0.6137	0.0410*
	All	0.2936	0.0110*
<i>Tylosaurus bernardi</i> (M)			
<i>Mosasaurus</i> sp. (M) –	PCo1-2	0.9160	0.0040**
	All	0.4207	0.0020**
<i>Cynthiacetus peruvianus</i> (C)			
<i>Tethysaurus nopcsai</i> (Rus) –	PCo1-2	0.0180	0.5045
	All	0.3131	0.0070**
<i>Plotosaurus bennisoni</i> (Plo)			
<i>Waipatia maerewhenua</i> (C) –	PCo1-2	0.8383	0.0090**
	All	0.5713	0***
<i>Gavialimimus almaghribensis</i> (M)			
<i>Aetiocetus cotylalveus</i> (Mys) –	PCo1-2	0.8573	0.0110*
	All	0.2080	0.0210*
<i>Xenorophus</i> sp. (Odo)			
<i>Simocetus rayi</i> (C) –	PCo1-2	0.7743	0.0160*
	All	0.1106	0.1918
<i>Selmasaurus johnsoni</i> (M)			

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1. Disparity analyses using the sum of variances metric, 1000 bootstrap replications.

Supplementary figure 2. Disparity analyses with the Oligocene mysticete *Janjucetus* removed. Sum of variances metric, 1000 bootstrap replications.

Supplementary figure 3. NMDS phylomorphospace with dietary information superimposed.

Taxa abbreviations: **B.i**, *Basilosaurus isis*; **C.p**, *Cynthiacetus peruvianus*; **D.a**, *Dorudon atrox*; **G.d**, *Globidens dakotensis*; **M.m**, *Mosasaurus missouriensis*; **M.s**, *Mystacodon selenensis*; **P.b**, *Plotosaurus bennisoni*; **P.o**, *Prognathodon overtoni*; **P sp**, *Plioplatecarpus sp*; **P.t**, *Platecarpus tympaniticus*; **S.r**, *Simocetus rayi*; **T.b**, *Tylosaurus bernardi*; **T.nep**, *Tylosaurus nepaeolicus*; **T.p**, *Tylosaurus proriger*.

Supplementary figure 4. NMDS phylomorphospace with all taxa labelled. Taxa abbreviations: **A.c**, *Aetiocetus cotylalveus*; **A sp**, *Agorophius* sp; **A.t**, *Ankylorhiza tiedemani*; **A.w**, *Aetiocetus weltoni*; **B.i**, *Basilosaurus isis*; **C.h**, *Coronodon havensteini*; **C.m**, *Cotylocara macei*; **C.p**, *Cynthiacetus peruvianus*; **C sp**, *Clidastes* sp.; **D.a**, *Dorudon atrox*; **E.c**, *Ectenosaurus clidastoides*; **E sp**, *Eosqualodon* sp; **G.a**, *Gavialimimus almaghribensis*; **G.d**, *Globidens dakotensis*; **H.a**, *Halisaurus arambourgi*; **J.h**, *Janjucetus hunderi*; **K sp**, *Kekenodon* sp; **OU 22397**, undescribed odontocete from the University of Otago; **M.I**, *Mosasaurus lemonnieri*; **M.m**, *Mosasaurus missouriensis*; **M.s**, *Mystacodon selenensis*; **M sp**, *Mosasaurus* aff. *hoffmanni*; **P.b**, *Plotosaurus bennisoni*; **P.c**, *Prognathodon currii*; **P.o**, *Prognathodon overtoni*; **P.p**, *Plesioplatecarpus planifrons*; **P.s**, *Prognathodon solvayi*; **P sp**, *Plioplatecarpus* sp; **P.t**, *Platecarpus tympaniticus*; **R.c**, *Russellosaurus coheni*; **S.j**, *Selmasaurus johnsoni*; **S.r**, *Simocetus rayi*; **T.b**, *Tylosaurus bernardi*; **T.ne**, *Tylosaurus nepaeolicus*; **T.no**, *Tethysaurus nopcsai*; **T.p**, *Tylosaurus proriger*; **W.m**, *Waipatia maerewhenua*; **X sp**, *Xenorophus* sp.

Supplementary figure 5. Cetacean trait histograms, pairwise distribution and correlations (Pearson's correlation coefficient, * indicates significance at $\alpha = 0.05$, ** at $\alpha = 0.01$).

Supplementary figure 6. Mosasauroid trait histograms, pairwise distribution and correlations (Pearson's correlation coefficient, * indicates significance at alpha = 0.05, ** at alpha = 0.01). Relative symphysis length was removed due to low taxon coverage.

Supplementary figure 7. PCoA phylomorphospace. Taxa abbreviations: **A.c**, *Aetiocetus cotylalveus*; **A sp**, *Agorophius sp*; **A.t**, *Ankylorhiza tiedemani*; **A.w**, *Aetiocetus weltoni*; **B.i**, *Basilosaurus isis*; **C.h**, *Coronodon havensteini*; **C.m**, *Cotylocara macei*; **C.p**, *Cynthiacetus peruvianus*; **C sp**, *Clidastes sp.*; **D.a**, *Dorudon atrox*; **E.c**, *Ectenosaurus clidastoides*; **E sp**, *Eosqualodon sp*; **G.a**, *Gavialimimus almaghribensis*; **G.d**, *Globidens dakotensis*; **H.a**, *Halisaurus arambourgi*; **J.h**, *Janjucetus hunderi*; **K sp**, *Kekenodon sp*; **OU 22397**, undescribed odontocete from the University of Otago; **M.l**, *Mosasaurus lemonnieri*; **M.m**, *Mosasaurus missouriensis*; **M.s**, *Mystacodon selenensis*; **M sp**, *Mosasaurus aff. hoffmanni*; **P.b**, *Plotosaurus bennisoni*; **P.c**, *Prognathodon currii*; **P.o**, *Prognathodon overtoni*; **P.p**, *Plesioplatecarpus planifrons*; **P.s**, *Prognathodon solvayi*; **P sp**, *Plioplatecarpus sp*; **P.t**, *Platecarpus tympaniticus*; **R.c**, *Russellosaurus coheni*; **S.j**, *Selmasaurus johnsoni*; **S.r**, *Simocetus rayi*; **T.b**, *Tylosaurus bernardi*; **T.ne**, *Tylosaurus nepaeolicus*; **T.no**, *Tethysaurus nopcsai*; **T.p**, *Tylosaurus proriger*; **W.m**, *Waipatia maerewhenua*; **X sp**, *Xenorophus sp*.

Supplementary figure 8. NMDS phylomorphospace with locomotory information superimposed. Taxa abbreviations: **A.c**, *Aetiocetus cotylalveus*; **A.t**, *Ankylorhiza tiedemani*; **B.i**, *Basilosaurus isis*; **C.p**, *Cynthiacetus peruvianus*; **C sp**, *Clidastes* sp.; **D.a**, *Dorudon atrox*; **Ec**, *Ectenosaurus clidastoides*; **M.s**, *Mystacodon selenensis*; **P.b**, *Plotosaurus bennisoni*; **P.o**, *Prognathodon overtoni*; **P sp**, *Plioplatecarpus* sp; **P.t**, *Platecarpus tympaniticus*; **R.c**, *Russellosaurus coheni*; **T.nop**, *Tethysaurus nopcsai*;

Supplementary figure 9. NMDS stress plot, showing the relationship between the actual dissimilarities between objects (from the original dissimilarity matrix) and the ordination distances on the NMDS morphospace. The strong correlation between these two variables shows a low ordination stress and indicates the NMDS results can be trusted.

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